

PSYCHONEUROLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN PREMATURE INFANTS WITH PERINATAL DAMAGE TO THE NERVOUS SYSTEM

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Purpose: to evaluate the formation of psychoneurologic function of premature infants in the first year of life depending on the gestational age.

Materials and Methods. 94 newborns with perinatal CNS lesions with different gestational age were examined. The children were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 - 17 premature neonates with extremely low birth weight (ELBW). Group 2 - 36 premature neonates with very low birth weight (VLBW); Group 3 - 41 premature neonates with low birth weight (LBW).

Results. A linear relationship of direct type between the strength of functional brain damage and clinical aggravations of perinatal CNS disorder on the background of hypoxia was noted, which was assessed by the Zhurba-Mastyukova scale and on the basis of EEG patterns. In the study at 12 months of age corrected children of all 3 groups were predominantly children with a variant of norm, developmental delay was found in groups 1, 2, 3 in 35,2%, 11,1%, 7,3% of cases respectively, cerebral palsy was diagnosed in 17,6% of children of group 1, in groups 2 and 3 - 5,5% and 2,4% respectively.

Conclusion. The action of damaging factors on the immature brain determines the variety of combinations of motor disorders, and also serves as a basis for impairments of cognitive and motor functions, which should be taken into account when justifying the restorative treatment and social rehabilitation of patients using an effective program, continuous stage-by-stage sequential multidisciplinary rehabilitation of premature infants, aimed at preventing pathological conditions and normalizing the rate of child development.

Key words: extremely low birth weight, premature infants, neurological complications.

During the first year of life, brain development plays a significant role in assessing and understanding a child's development. Every ability and skill a child acquires is the result of neuropsychiatric activity. Due to this fact, the development of certain abilities relative to his age can be an indicator of his overall health in the first 12 months of life [1, 5, 8, 9]. This study is of great importance, in particular for children born earlier than the optimal gestational period, which may result in pathologies of the unequal system, which include cerebral palsy in the earliest periods of the child's life [2,3]. Determining expected developmental indicators for preterm infants, especially those who are profoundly premature, is challenging. The degree of prematurity, morphofunctional immaturity and the presence of perinatal pathologies lead to differences in the development of psychomotor functions compared with their preterm peers [3,4,7]. Due to these factors, a multistage system of early detection of nervous system defects and the probability of cerebral palsy development should be created. Studies aimed at identifying risk factors, prediction and outcomes of this lesion, as well as assessing the health, physical and psychomotor development of children in this group with the improvement of preventive, diagnostic, therapeutic

and rehabilitation approaches, play an important role in solving the problem of disability of such children. Determining the purpose of such research is an urgent task.

Purpose Of The Study. To evaluate the formation of psychoneurological function of premature infants in the first year of life depending on the gestational age.

Materials And Methods Of Research. 94 newborns with perinatal CNS lesions with different gestational age were selected. The children were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 - 17 neonates, 29.4±0.12 weeks gestation, with extremely low body weight (ENMT), 855.5±15.8 g; Group 2 - 36 premature neonates, 32.3±0.2 weeks. of gestation, with very low birth weight (VLBW) - 1508.5±145.47 g; group 3 - 41 premature infants of 35.5±0.9 weeks of gestation, with low birth weight (LBW) - 2126.0±119.7 g; and group 3 - 41 premature infants of 35.5±0.9 weeks of gestation, with low birth weight (LBW) - 2126.0±119.7 g;

Results And Their Discussion. Assessment of the neuropsychiatric status of premature newborns has multidirectional processes depending on the intensity of manifestation of pathological processes in the central nervous system and is in close correlation with the gestational age at birth. The analysis of neurological status for the period of early neonatal period in children of groups 1 and 2 revealed the prevalence of cerebral depression syndrome, which amounted to 35.2 and 47.2%, respectively. The CNS oppression syndrome was characterized by decreased spontaneous motor activity and reaction to examination with floating movements of the eyeballs, muscle hypotonia, decreased periosteal reflexes and reflexes of the newborn period. Convulsive syndrome occurred in groups 1, 2 and 3 in 5.8%, 5.5%, 2.4% of cases, respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Neurological syndromes of the examined newborn children in the neonatal period (%)

At 3, 6, and 12 months of age, psychomotor development was assessed using the Zhurba-Mastyukova scale. At 3 months of examination according to the corrected age, children with risk of neurological complications (27-30 points) prevailed in all 3 groups, while developmental delay (13-22 points) prevailed in group 1 children 3.6 times more than in groups 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Clinical evaluation of premature infants according to the Zhurba-Mastyukova scale at 6 months of age

At 6 months of age, group 1 children had a predominant developmental delay of 70.5%, while in group 2 the risk of neurological complications was noted in 52.7% of cases, which

indicates positive dynamics of development of children in this group, developmental delay was in 25% of children. In group 3, by 6 months of corrected age, the rate of normality was 41.4%, developmental delay was observed in 19.5% of cases (Fig. 2). At the 12-month corrected age study, children of all 3 groups had predominantly normal variant, developmental delay decreased in groups 1, 2, and 3 to 35.2%, 11.1%, and 7.3% of cases, respectively.

Fig3. Electroencephalographic study in dynamics at 6 months of age

An instrumental study by electroencephalography (EEG) was performed. On EEG at 6 months of life in children of group 1 and group 2, type I (normal) was found in 11.7% and 19.4% of cases, respectively. The second type (“maturation delay”) was observed in children of groups 1, 2, and 3 in 52.9%; 61.1%; and 53.6% of cases, respectively. The third type (“impaired maturation”) was slightly more common in children of group 1 (23.5%) compared to group 2 (13.8%). The fourth type (“pathology”) occurred only in group 1 and group 2 children 11.7% and 5.5%, respectively (Fig3).

Figure 4. Electroencephalographic study in dynamics at 12 months of age

When examining the children in dynamics at 12 months, the correlation between the degree of disturbance of the functional state of the brain and the nature of the structural lesion of the CNS was revealed.

At 12 months, type 1 prevailed in all groups of children, but type 2 persisted in groups 1 and 2, which amounted to 35.2% and 22.2%, respectively. Type 3 maturation disorders in Group 1 were observed in 17.6% of children (Fig. 4). Subsequently, as the brain matures structurally and functionally in postnatal ontogenesis, the characteristics of the EEG pattern can have a pronounced positive dynamics, approaching the normative ones.

Table 1. Dynamics and outcomes of neurologic syndromes

Syndromes	1 group		2 group		3 group	
	6 month	12 month	6 month	12 month	6 month	12 month
Disorder of tone and motor skills	47%	5,8%	25%	11,1%	19,5%	17%
Cerebral agitation	0%	0	13,8%	0	7,3%	0
Vegeto-visceral disorders	35,2%	5,8%	36,1%	13,8%	60,9%	14,6%
Cerebral vascular distension	17,6%	11,7%	22,2%	11,1%	12,1%	7,3%
Risk of cerebral palsy	52,9%	17,6%	22,2%	5,5%	9,7%	2,4%

Delayed developmental tones		23,5%		11,1%		9,7%
No neurological deficit		35,2%		47,2%		48,7%

At 6 months of corrected age the risk of infant cerebral palsy (ICP) development was revealed, which amounted to 52.2%, 17.6%, 9.7% of cases in group 1, 2 and 3, respectively. A significant correlation of cerebral palsy formation in children with the average gestational age was revealed ($r=0.58$). By 12 months of corrected age, 17.6% of children of group 1 and 5.5% and 2.4% of children of groups 2 and 3 were diagnosed with organic lesions of the CNS (cerebral palsy), respectively, which is 4 times less than at 6 months of age. Also at this age, the number of children without neurological deficit was 35.2% in Group 1, 47.2% in Group 2, and 48.7% in Group 3 (Table).

Conclusion. Thus, the conducted studies have once again confirmed that the actions of damaging factors on the immature brain determine the variety of combinations of motor disorders, as well as serve as a basis for disorders of cognitive and motor functions, which should be taken into account when justifying the restorative treatment and social rehabilitation of patients using an effective program, continuous stage-by-stage sequential multidisciplinary rehabilitation of premature infants, aimed at preventing pathological conditions and normalizing.

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